

D-JRP-PARADISE-WP4.4
Report of interlaboratory
comparison of post-DNA
extraction hybridization
probe capture and MC-PCR
for *C. parvum* and *G.*
duodenalis

Workpackage 4 of
JRP19-ET1.1-PARADISE

Responsible Partners: P-41 SVA, P-30
RIVM

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D-JRP-PARADISE-WP4. REPORT OF INTERLABORATORY COMPARISON OF POST-DNA EXTRACTION HYBRIDIZATION PROBE CAPTURE AND MC-PCR FOR *C. PARVUM* AND *G. DUODENALIS*

Background

This is a public deliverable of One Health EJP Joint Research Project:

JRP19-ET1.1-PARADISE – PARASite Detection, ISolation and Evaluation

(<https://onehealthjep.eu/jrp-paradise/>);

Work Package:

JRP- PARADISE –WP4 Parasite enrichment strategies;

Task:

JRP-PARADISE-PARADISE-WP4-T2 Development of post-DNA extraction enrichment strategies.

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PARADISE aims to increase the understanding of *Cryptosporidium* and *Giardia* genomics and through that knowledge design novel multi-locus typing schemes (MLST) with much improved resolution. To be able to use the novel MLST, PARADISE will develop and test novel enrichment strategies to overcome the limitations of current technologies, including pre-DNA extraction and post-DNA extraction enrichment approaches.

PARADISE WP4 aims to develop approaches to detect *Cryptosporidium* and *Giardia* (oo)cyst contamination in food through the development of parasite enrichment strategies, which should improve the sensitivity of detection and deliver cost effective methods applicable to food matrices.

Objectives of PARADISE WP4 are:

- ✓ To develop two pre-DNA extraction protocols based on two alternative affinity reagents, nanobodies (single-chain variable fragment antibodies) and aptamers (oligonucleotides that bind to specific target molecules);

- ✓ To assess nanobodies and aptamers application for magnetic capture of *C. parvum* and *G. duodenalis* (oo)cysts in different matrices;
- ✓ To develop a protocol for post-DNA enrichment to concentrate parasite DNA based on hybridization of target-specific biotinylated probes.
- ✓ To evaluate pre- and post-DNA extraction enrichment strategies by inter-laboratory comparison

This deliverable reports on the third objective of PARADISE WP4, namely the design and testing of hybridization biotinylated, single-stranded DNA probes specific to pull-out DNA of *C. parvum* or *G. duodenalis* from complex DNA solutions.

Figure 1. Illustration of WP4. D) is task WP4-T2, post-DNA extraction enrichment of specific markers. Figure is adopted from the PARADISE proposal

The objective of task WP4-T2 is the development and evaluation of a protocol for post-DNA extraction enrichment based on sequence-based capture of low abundance target DNA in matrices such as faeces, water (drinking, recreational and wastewater as well as washing water from fresh produce) and archived DNA from suspected foodborne outbreaks.

It has been reported (D-JRP-PARADISE-WP4.3 and D-JRP-PARADISE-WP4.8) on the development of new hybridization capture probe systems, the validation of these and the Standard Operating Procedures written. Herein we report on the interlaboratory comparison of these capture probes developed for *C. parvum* 18S rDNA and gp60 loci.

Description of the Ring test

During the final Paradise meeting in Uppsala (June 2022) it was decided to perform an interlaboratory comparison for the developed capture probe system. All participants that had offered to run the ring test during the writing of the proposal, plus one additional Institute that later volunteered to participate, were invited. An email with the SOP and description of the RT was sent to the 8 participants with the offer to receive material. Five institutes responded, all willing to do the RT. Samples were shipped in October 2022 along with an updated SOP and most reagents needed for the work. The samples included in the RT are presented in table 1. Due to time constraints each laboratory was asked to return the results within 3 weeks of dispatch. SVA offered a hands-on training before the RT. Two institutes sent representatives to SVA for a two-day training in the lab.

Table 1. Samples used for the ring test

Sample 1	Positive <i>C. parvum</i> faecal sample from calf
Sample 2	Sample 1 diluted 1:10 in <i>Cryptosporidium</i> negative faecal sample
Sample 3	Sample 1 diluted 1:100 in <i>Cryptosporidium</i> negative faecal sample
Sample 4	<i>Cryptosporidium</i> negative faecal sample

Each participant was asked to follow the SOP and prepare the samples for lysis and DNA capture using magnetic beads. The results were to be evaluated using the result of qPCR for each of the loci. The results reported to SVA were Cq values for each qPCR, including values for the internal amplification control. Participants were also asked to report any issues they found when using the SOP.

Results and conclusions

The result from the five participating Institutes are presented in Tables 2 and 3. One partner (number 3) had issues with the qPCR and the results were therefore not considered. For the remaining four Institutes the results look overall good. For Institutes 1 and 5, the Cq values are lower for gp60 than for 18S rDNA, which is surprising considering that the 18S rDNA is a multicopy gene. For participants 1, 2, 4 and 5 the results in the dilution series were in line with the expectations based on the dilution factor, although variation between labs was observed. The participating labs provided valuable feedback regarding the SOP, which was taken into consideration when finalizing it.

Table 2: Results from interlaboratory comparison on *gp60* locus

Institute	Sample 1		Sample 2		Sample 3		Sample 4		No sample control	
	triplicates	average	triplicates	average	triplicates	average	triplicates	average	triplicates	average
1	22,55		25,31		28,66		-		-	
	22,77	22,81	25,36	25,13	28,62	28,58	40,12		-	
	23,12		24,73		28,47		-		-	
2	23,86		26,77		30,07		-		-	
	23,83	23,84	26,51	26,68	30,08	30,05	-		-	
	23,83		26,76		29,99		-		-	
3*	-		-		34,28		-		-	
4	27,94		30,06		33,40		-		-	
	27,60	27,78	29,98	30,13	33,09	33,18	-		-	
	27,81		30,34		33,06		-		-	
5	23,14		26,86		30,02		-		-	
	23,00	23,21	26,85	26,83	29,63	29,85	-		-	

23,48 26,78 29,91 - -

*Institute 3 only reported one result per sample

Table 3: Results from interlaboratory comparison on 18S rDNA locus

Institute	Sample 1		Sample 2		Sample 3		Sample 4		No sample control	
	triplicates	average	triplicates	average	triplicates	average	triplicates	average	triplicates	average
1	25,14		26,19		30,07		-		-	
	24,06	24,73	26,24	26,39	30,61	30,34	-		-	
	24,99		26,75		30,35		-		-	
2	21,69	21,67	24,02	23,98	27,00	27,02	-		-	
	21,66		23,99		27,06		-		-	
	21,66		23,93		26,99		-		-	
3	-		-		30,52		43,29		-	
4	25,06		27,17		30,53		-		-	
	24,71	24,79	27,23	27,09	29,12	29,64	-		-	
	24,60		26,88		29,26		-		-	
5	24,80		27,53		30,92		-		-	
	24,87	24,57	28,54	27,99	30,90	30,76	-		-	
	24,04		27,91		30,45		-		-	

*Institute 3 only reported one result per sample

The results from the RT confirmed that the SOP was correctly implemented and used by the participating laboratories. Partner institute 3 has been given the opportunity to repeat the qPCRs and report new results but the time was insufficient to allow for this.